

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE DIARRHEA DISEASES IN CHILDREN

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Abstract

Due to the fact that acute diarrheal diseases, under the influence of many climatic and social factors, sometimes have an unsatisfactory course with the formation of invasive diarrhea syndrome, and also cause various complications and often turn into chronic forms, and today it continues to be an urgent problem for pediatricians and children's infectious disease specialists. Diarrhea is a syndrome that is estimated as a violation of intestinal function accompanied by acceleration of defecation when the intestine is damaged by toxins, bacteria and viruses. Currently, acute intestinal infections (AII), accompanied by diarrhea, occupy second place in the structure of infectious diseases after respiratory viral infections. According to WHO statistics, more than 1 billion people fall ill every year in the world, and 65-70% of them are children under 5 years of age. It has already been established that diarrhea is the second leading cause of child mortality. According to statistics, in 2017, 1.8 million children under the age of 5 years died from diarrheal diseases [1,6,8]. 40% of hospitalized patients with infectious diseases make up OKI. In recent years, despite the introduction into medical practice of the most modern laboratory-diagnostic methods and the use of a wide spectrum of action of drugs in the treatment of these diseases, doctors working in the system of practical health care still face many difficulties in the diagnosis and treatment of AII of bacterial origin (in connection with the resistance of pathogens) [2,9].

Keywords: child, diarrhea, acute intestinal infection, dysbacteriosis, intestinal microflora.

Goal of the work: Comparative assessment of the clinical features of acute diarrheal diseases in children of different ages.

Material and methods: studies were conducted on 86 young children: 54 patients with acute diarrheal diseases of established etiology (n=54), 32 patients with acute diarrheal diseases of unknown etiology (n=32). 30 healthy children (n=30) were selected as a control group. Among 86 children with diarrhea under observation, 52 (60.5%) were boys, 34 (39.5%) were girls. The patients were divided into 3 age groups: Group I 4-12 months 35 (40.7%); Group II 1-2 years 37 (43.0%); Group III 14 (16.3%) patients aged 2-3 years. The vast majority of children with acute onset of the disease were hospitalized 73 (84.9%). These patients, along with anamnestic data, underwent general clinical and bacteriological studies.

Results. The clinical characteristics of diseases accompanied by acute diarrheal syndrome were studied taking into account the child's age, diet and etiology of the disease. When assessing the severity of the condition, it was found that between children with acute diarrhea of unknown etiology (n=54) and acute diarrhea of unknown etiology (n=32), moderate and severe diarrhea was more common. (61% and 74%, respectively), and relapses of the disease are significantly higher (38.6%) in children under 1 year of age. In other words, there is a direct relationship between the severity of the disease and the age of the child. The etiology of acute diarrhea was established in 71 (82.6%) patients using a bacteriological research method, PCR diagnosis was carried out in 52 (60.5%) patients. During examination

of 42 patients, the etiological factor of diarrhea was revealed to be of bacterial origin: salmonellosis - in 17 (31.5% - mainly in children under 1 year of age), dysentery - in 18 (33.3%) patients, in 7 (16.7%) patients - *E. Coli*. When analyzing the dependence of the frequency of acute diarrhea on the etiological factor, it was found that in children under 1 year of age, despite the predominance of salmonellosis (*Salmonella typhimurium* in our survey) compared to dysentery, with increasing age the proportion of dysentery in the etiology of acute diarrhea remains consistently high, and the frequency acute diarrheal diseases in children over 1 year of age are generally 3 times higher than in children under 1 year of age. This trend is also evident for certain diseases. Since the proportion of *Escherichia* infection in children under 1 year of age is 14.3%, then among children aged 1-3 years this figure almost doubles (22.9%). Among children under 1 year of age, acute diarrheal diseases of unknown etiology account for about 31.3%, which requires further improvement of laboratory diagnostic methods. When studying the dependence of cases of acute diarrhea on the type of diet, it was found that 37 (43%) children were mixed-fed, 24 (27.9%) children were naturally fed, and 26 (30.2%) children were bottle-fed. Among these children, diarrhea most often occurred in children fed too much mixed food. Cases of relapse and severe course of the disease, diarrhea was observed mainly in formula-fed children (61.7%). In our studies, diarrheal diseases,

which occurred mainly in the form of gastroenterocolitis (43.2%) and gastroenteritis (34.8%), did not reveal a significant difference between the compared groups in the localization of lesions in the gastrointestinal tract.

During the study, we also analyzed the clinical characteristics of symptom complexes of acute diarrhea in children under 1 year of age (n=35) and 1-3 years of age (n=51) with symptoms of acute diarrhea (Table 1).

Table 1

Comparative clinical characteristics of symptoms of acute diarrhea in children under 1 year and 1-3 years

Signs		Up to 1 year (n=35)		1-3 years (n=51)	
		abs	%	abs	%
onset of the disease	acute	24	68,6	38	74,5
	gradually	10	28,6	11	21,6
body temperature	norm	5	14,3	7	13,7
	>38	21	60	28	54,9
	<38	9	25,7	16	31,4
general weakness		35	100	51	100
slackness		35	100	51	100
pale skin		34	97,1	51	100
dry mucous membranes		35	100	51	100
coated tongue		34	97,1	51	100
sleep disorder		19	54,3	26	50,9
decreased appetite		33	94,3	49	96,1
Nausea		19	54,3	32	62,7
vomit	one by one	20	57,1	31	60,8
	numerous	6	17,1	7	13,7
abdominal pain		32	91,4	42	82,4
flatulence		23	65,7	30	58,8
pain in the sigmoid colon		12	34,3	22	43,1
tenesmus		8	22,8	18	35,3
stool character	liquid with slime	25	71,4	35	68,6
	with mucus and admixture of blood	7	20,0	12	23,5
	abundant watery	2	5,7	5	9,8
amount of stool	3-5	12	34,2	15	29,4
	5-10	19	54,3	25	49,0
	10-15	4	11,4	9	17,6
	>15	0	0	4	7,8
hepatomegaly		12	34,3	17	33,3

As can be seen from the table, the disease in both groups usually has an acute onset and is 68.6% and 74.5%, respectively. In both groups, the severity of the condition was determined primarily by impaired water-electrolyte metabolism and the development of intestinal toxicosis, and the manifestation of clinical signs was varied. However, among these signs in all children, general symptoms of intoxication were considered more characteristic: increased body temperature (60.0 and 54.9%, respectively), general weakness, lethargy, peeling of the skin, dry mucous membranes, dry tongue, sleep disturbances (54.3% and 50.9%), decreased appetite (94.3 and 96.1%). The severity of both the general toxic syndrome and local manifestations varies depending on age. Thus, if single cases of vomiting were recorded more often in children aged 1-3 years (60.8%) compared to children under 1 year of age (57.1%), then multiple vomiting was more often observed in children under 1 year of age (17, 1%). In both groups, there was a significant increase in the frequency of abdominal pain (91.4 and 82.4%, respectively) and bloating syndromes (65.7 and 58.8%). Pain in the sigmoid colon, attacks of tenesmus or their equivalents were more pronounced in children 1-3 years old (22.8

and 35.3, respectively). In addition to the indicated main clinical signs of the disease, all patients had diarrhea, among whom more transparent mucous stools were observed (71.4 and 68.6%, respectively) and bloody mucous stools (20.0 and 23.5%, respectively). In acute diarrheal diseases in 54.3% of children under 1 year and in 49.0% of children 1-3 years old, a 5-10-fold increase in the daily amount of stool lasting 12-14 days as the main symptom again confirms the leading role of diarrhea. An objective examination revealed hepatomegaly in 67.6% of patients, splenomegaly in 36.4%, pathological heart murmurs and wheezing in the lungs in 28.6%. For children under 1 year of age, mild dehydration and a toxic-dystrophic state are more typical, manifested by such symptoms as sharpness of facial features, large drooping and sunken eyes, decreased tissue turgor, dry mucous membranes and a burning sensation ($p > 0.01$), acute diarrhea in children 1-3 years old was accompanied by dehydration and exicosis of the first degree. In acute diarrheal diseases, due to an increase in the daily number of bowel movements and persistence of stool disorders, even after the cessation of antibacterial therapy and the end of the inflam-

matory process in order to study the intestinal microbiota, a microbiological study of stool was carried out in all children. Taking into account the acceleration of defecation and the persistence of stool abnormalities even after the cessation of antibacterial therapy and the end of the course of treatment for acute diarrheal diseases in order to study the intestinal microbiosis was carried out a microbiological study of stool in all children. During these examinations, the presence of dysbacteriosis of varying degrees was confirmed in all (100%) children: in 16 (18.6%) patients - degree I, in 46 (53.5%) patients - degree II, in 14 (16, 3%) - Patients with grade III dysbacteriosis. In 64.2% of patients, a deficiency of bifidobacteria, 66.8% of lactobacilli and 37.4% of *Escherichia coli* was determined. At the same time, fungi of the genus *Candida*, *Klebsiella* and *Proteus* were detected in significant titers in some children. One of the issues that drew attention was that despite the disappearance of clinical symptoms during therapy, the recovery of the body in all children occurs very slowly. This situation was once again confirmed by the identification of the pathogen in 1/3 of the children at the 3-4th week of the disease and the persistence of varying degrees of intestinal dysbiosis during repeated microbiological studies.

Conclusion. Thus, we can conclude that in modern times, during acute diarrheal diseases, a number of different changes are observed, which manifests itself in the fact that diarrheal diseases in most patients become moderate and severe forms, the recovery process lasts up to 3-4 weeks, and pathogens acquire multiresistance to antibiotics. In our study, a severe course of the disease with an unsatisfactory outcome in some children was more often associated with a severe intoxication syndrome, clearly defined disturbances of water-electrolyte metabolism and immunodeficiency, and in rare cases with congenital background diseases.

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